

Table 1. Performance of Zhongyu 87-1 in late season hybrid rice demonstration test.^a Zhejiang, China, 1988.

Location	Height (m)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over Shanyou 6 (%)
Quxian	78.7	9.7	99.3	10.6	29.4	7.1	14.8
Huangyan	81.0	10.3	105.7	13.6	30.8	7.5	5.0
Fuying	83.8	10.4	112.6	12.0	27.8	8.8	42.0
Shuichang	75.1	10.9	91.9	23.1	26.9	5.1	-3.5
Wenlin	-	11.3	116.1	9.7	26.1	8.3	14.3
Leqing	-	12.0	111.6	15.4	27.5	7.4	2.2

^aPlot size = 133 m².

lodging resistance. Panicles are large (106-110 grains/panicle) and grain-filling rate high (85%), with 27-29 g/1,000 grains and 22-23% amylose content. In 1989, Zhongyu 87-1 was promoted to regional adaptability tests in Hubei and Zhejiang. □

Table 2. Yield of Zhongyu 87-1 in midseason rice preliminary regional adaptability tests. Hubei, China, 1988.

Location	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase over Quichao 2 (%)	Rank in test ^b
Wuhan	7.1**	16.5	1
Dongxihu	9.6**	11.6	2
Jinzhou	8.5**	17.3	1

^aOf 11 varieties. ** = significant at P = 0.01.

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Data management and computer modeling

Simulation of yield potential in rice cultivars

R. Sadasivam, S. Mohandass, and A. Arjunan, *Crop Physiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore*; and S. Palanisamy and N. Raju, *Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India*

We raised six lowland rice cultivars available from the gene bank of the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, during 1988 wet season and conducted productivity studies. Yield potentials were computer simulated using the MACROS. L1D simulation model developed by IRRI.

Calculated and measured main yield of rice cultivars at Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivar	Calculated grain yield (t/ha)	Measured grain yield (t/ha)	Simulation percentage
ADT36	6.8	6.2	91.2
ADT37	5.1	4.8	94.1
CO 37	7.2	7.0	97.2
ASD16	5.2	5.1	98.1
TKM6	2.3	3.1	134.8
IR66	4.1	5.6	136.6

The program took into account dry matter accumulation, physiological characteristics, and weather prevailing during the growth period.

Observed and calculated grain yield are presented in the table. Measured grain yields within 10% ±100% of calculated grain yield are presented in the figure.

Calculated grain yield and measured yield agree satisfactorily in ADT36, ADT37, CO 37, and ASD16.

This shows that yield potential and production can be reasonably estimated on the basis of cultivar physiological characteristics and growing area weather conditions. □

Calculated and measured grain yield for rice cultivars. Coimbatore, India.

Seed technology

Screening rice varieties for grain dormancy

S. L. Kumary, S. K. Ommen, and C. A. Joseph, *Kerala Agricultural University, Rice Research Station (RRS), Moncompu, India*

Harvest of the second (Feb-Jun) crop at Kuttanad usually coincides with the rainy season. Popular high-yielding varieties grown during the second season lack seed dormancy and considerable loss occurs due to grain sprouting in the field.

We screened germplasm at RRS Moncompu for grain dormancy to

Grain dormancy^a of rice varieties and cultures in Kuttanad, India.

Strong dormancy	Moderate dormancy
Chennellu, Karivennel, Kuruka, Pokkali 372, Chettiviruppu, RP 106, MO 1, MO 4, Cul. 12814, 31-2-1, 126, 168, 83-1-1, 65-2-3-1, 23-7-1-1, 14-14-2-3, 305-2, 106-1-1	Vykatharyan, Nandiarvattom, Sulekha, Cul. 93, 170, 1459-2, 214-1, 166-1-2, OS4, 1539-2

^aStrong = 5-25% dormancy, moderate = 25-50% dormancy.

identify donor parents for developing appropriate varieties.

Test cultivars included local tall indica varieties, high-yielding varieties, and prerelease japonica/ indica cultures. Panicles were collected 1 wk before maturity, at maturity, and 1 wk after maturity and sun-dried to 13-14% moisture. The dried panicles were soaked 12 h in water, drained, and kept at room temperature 36 h to measure germination.

Of the 85 entries screened, 28 possessed moderate to strong dormancy (see table). □

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CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Crop management

Yields of broadcast and transplanted *Oryza glaberrima* floating rice

W. Schreurs, UNDP/UNCDF, Mali, West Africa

Despite the generally assumed superiority of *O. sativa*, many farmers in West Africa still prefer *O. glaberrima*. In field observations in Tombouctou, Mali, *O. glaberrima* was more drought tolerant and had greater vegetative vigor than *O. sativa* varieties grown in Mali.

Yields of *O. glaberrima* in farmers' fields averaged 2.5 t/ha (highest yield

was 4.4 t/ha) (Table 1). One reason for the relatively high yield may be that the crop is harvested at maximum water levels (from canoes), when culms are standing upright in the water. Crop disturbance and subsequent grain shattering (the primary cause of low *O. glaberrima* yields) are kept to a minimum.

Because of frequent crop failure due to lack of rain, farmers recently have begun to try transplanting floating rice in floodwater. The data seem to indicate that yields of transplanted floating rice are lower than those of broadcast rice. However, only four fields of transplanted rice were surveyed. We studied transplanting in a single-replication trial (plot size 13 m²) using both *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima* varieties (Table 2). Four-wk-old

Table 1. *O. glaberrima* floating rice yields in farmers' fields. Tombouctou, Mali, 1987.

Village	Variety	Establishment	Yield ^a (t/ha)
Tourchauane	Dembu	Broadcast	3.7
Tourchauane	Dembu	Broadcast	3.4
Tourchauane	Dembu	Broadcast	4.4
Gourzougouay	Dembu	Broadcast	0.7
Gourzougouay	Dembu	Broadcast	2.3
Gourzougouay	Dembu	Broadcast	1.4
Banikane	Dembu	Broadcast	1.4
Banikane	Dembu	Broadcast	1.4
Hondou bomo koyna	Jinga	Broadcast	2.6
Hondou bomo koyna	Jinga	Broadcast	2.5
Hondou bomo koyna	Jinga	Broadcast	2.3
Hondou bomo koyna	Dembu	Broadcast	3.2
Bozo	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	3.4
Bozo	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	3.1
Chembu	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	3.1
Chembu	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	2.0
Chembu	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	3.6
Chembu	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	3.0
Chembu	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	1.6
Sanfatou	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	1.4
Bougouni	Dembu	Broadcast ^b	1.5
Average yield			2.5
Bori	Jinga	Transplanted	2.4
Bori	Jinga	Transplanted	2.3
Hondou bomo koyna	Kossa	Transplanted	1.2
Hondou bomo koyna	Dembu	Transplanted	1.2
Average yield			1.8

^aSample plot size was 25 m², 10% was deducted from sample dry weight to account for sampling errors. ^bReceived some additional irrigation (by motor pump) during establishment.

Table 2. Grain yield and growth duration of transplanted floating rice. Tombouctou, Mali, 1987.

	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)
<i>Oryza glaberrima</i>		
Dembu cirai	3.9	112
Dembu banekanna	2.9	112
Kossa bibi	2.2	103
Jinga	1.4	90
<i>Oryza sativa</i>		
FFRS43-3	3.7	120
DM16	3.5	117
Nang Kieuw	2.3	125
Khao Gaew	0.8	130